

Storage Tools at the <Uni>

As of 25.03.2025

Features		Provided by the <Uni> Shared drives		Provided externally		
		Department of ...		Personal Account	Sciebo	Projectbox
Storage space	How much?	50 GB	200 GB	30 GB (500 GB for employees*)	2 TB per project	100 GB per project
	What type of data?	Personal data	Research data	Data	Research data	Research data
	How long?	For the duration of employment	For the duration of the project	1 year, extension possible	2 years, extension possible	Until 10 years after the project ended (even if the person is no longer part of the H-BRS)
	What happens to data if I'm no longer part of the H-BRS?	Deletion after 1 year		Deletion after max. 1 year after the last extension	Ownership is transferable	
	Expandable?	X	✓	500 GB for employees*	X	125 TB by application
Access	From where?	Requires uni network or VPN		X	X	X
		Browser access		✓	✓	✓
		Offline (Synchronization)		✓	✓	X
	Who?	Students		✓	✓	✓
		Employees*		✓	✓	✓
	External		X	X	✓	
Data Protection	Access control?	Person specific	By project	Person specific	By role	By role
	Are editing rights adjustable?	X	✓	X	X	
	Where are my data stored?	<Uni>	<Uni>	NRW	NRW	NRW
Data security	Geo-Redundant storage	✓	✓	X	X	✓
	Automatic back-ups?	✓	✓	X	X	✓
Extras	Includes collaborative working tools?	X	X	Overleaf, OnlyOffice	Overleaf, OnlyOffice	X
	Metadata?	X	X	X	X	✓
	Versioning?	X	X	✓	✓	X
Costs						
Description	Department-specific centralized storage systems to store, manage, and share files among multiple users (in most cases employees only). Shared drives can be accessed like local drives (e.g. like C: on Windows, /home on Linux and /Users on mac).			A non-commercial cloud storage by universities for universities, where you can securely store your research, study and teaching data. There are personal accounts for single people and project boxes for work groups that work with very large amounts of data. Project boxes are particularly suited for long-term projects with changing project management.		Research data management platform for your research project. Here your data becomes FAIR – from storage, description with metadata, collaboration with all participating researchers to archiving.
Additional information						System can be linked with Gitlab and Uni resources. Fully comprehensive offer for employees and project participants only.
Documentation & Contact						Sciebo Documentation
*Employees mean research associates, professors and other non-student employees only (keine Hilfskräfte)						